

Insect pest incidence in pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan* L. Millsp) in Bundelkhand region of Uttar Pradesh, India

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Original Research Article Received on March 10, 2020 Revised on March 26, 2020 Accepted on April 04, 2020 Published on April 17, 2020</p> <p>Article Authors Sundar Pal, Prabhat Tiwari Corresponding Author Email sun.csaent@gmail.com</p>	<p>The observation was recorded on ten major insect pest of pigeon pea crop during zaid season, 2019. A category of insect was recorded on four sucking and six solid feeder insect. The population of Jassid, cowbug and leaf webber were recorded from 32nd SW to 50th SW where population rang was 0.33±0.58-6.67±2.31, 0.67±0.19-3.00±0.33 and 1.33±0.58-9.33±0.58 insect/week, respectively. The maximum population of pod bug (10.67±1.53 bug/plant/week), green bug (5.00±1.0053 bug/plant/week), spotted pod borer (8.67±0.58 larvae/plant/week), blister beetle (2.67±1.15 adults/plant/week), pod fly (5.00±1.00 larvae/plant/week), pod borer (8.33±0.58 larvae/plant/week) and plum moth (4.33±0.58 larvae/plant/week) were recorded from 10th, 44th, 48th, 44th, 45th, 49th and 49th SW, respectively.</p>
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Pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan* L. Millsp) is an important grain legume crop of the tropics and subtropics regions. It is also known as tur, arhar and red gram. Pigeon pea is rich source of protein (22.3%), which supplies a major share of the protein requirement of the vegetarian population of the country, making it evaluable component for improving food security and nutrition for many poor families (Tiwari and Shivhare, 2016). Pigeon pea is a multi-purpose crop used as dal (split grains), vegetable (green seeds and pods), fodder (green and dry leaves), feed (dry crushed grains) and fuel. It helps in nitrogen fixation and can be grown for green manuring. Pigeon pea occupies an area of 7.03 million hectares in the world with annual production of 4.89 million tonnes.

In India, it is grown on 5.60 million hectares with an annual production and productivity of 3.29 million tonnes and 587.3 kg/ha, respectively, (FAO 2014). Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Punjab, Haryana and Gujarat are the major pigeon pea growing state in India. Pigeon pea is the second most important pulse crop next to chickpea sharing 16.38% of total pulse production during 2014-15 (Anonymous, 2017). In Haryana, it is cultivated on an area of 15.1 thousand hectares with production and productivity of 16.4 thousand tonnes and 1086 kg/ha, respectively, (Anonymous, 2014). More than 250 insect species have been recorded feeding on pigeon pea and among these only few cause

significant and consistent damage (Keval *et al.*, 2017).

Materials and Methods

Data was collected from Crop Cafeteria, Rani Lakshmi Bai Central Agricultural University, Jhansi, UP, India during 2019. Three plants randomly selected from each plot and count total numbers of insect from hall plant for cow bug, pod bug, green bug, spotted pod borer, blister beetle, pod borer and plume moth. Observation on jassid population selected three leaves from lower, middle and top of plant and count a total numbers of maggots present in per infested pod.

Results and Discussion

Data was recorded on the population of jassid or leaf hopper, *Empoasca fabae* Harris in pigeon pea from Crop Cafeteria during 2019. The population was first time recorded from 32nd standard week (SW) with 0.33 ± 0.58 individuals/leave/week. The peak population of jassid (6.67 ± 2.31 individuals/leave/week) was observed at 46th SW. Jassid population was continue noticed from the crop plants during study period. Surana (2001) found that *E. kerri* appeared from seedling to pod formation stage of the crop with its peak activity, in first week of October. A range of 0.1 to 1.0 insects per plant was observed during the infestation. Pandey and Das (2014) found that population of *Empoasca fabae* on pigeon pea first appeared during the first week of September i.e. 36th standard meteorological week (SMW) and continued up to third week of January. The higher population of the pest was observed during 42nd SMW to 48th SMW.

Population of cow bug (*Otinotus oneratus* W.) was started with 0.67 ± 0.19 individuals /plant /week and it was noticed 1.33 ± 0.19 individuals /plant/week at the end of the season. The population range was recorded 0.67 ± 0.19 - 3.00 ± 0.33 individuals /plant/week. The peak population was recorded from three times, first from 37th, second from 38th and third from 40th SW. Cow bug population was not severe during study period. Incidence of leaf webber, *Grapholita critica* (Meyr) was noticed from 32nd SW to continue end of season. The pest incidence was 1.33 ± 0.58 , 1.33 ± 0.58 , 2.33 ± 0.58 , 2.67 ± 0.58 , 3.67 ± 0.58 , 3.67 ± 1.15 , 4.33 ± 0.58 ,

5.00 ± 1.00 , 6.67 ± 0.58 , 7.67 ± 0.58 , 8.33 ± 0.58 , 8.33 ± 1.15 , 8.67 ± 0.58 , 9.33 ± 0.58 , 7.00 ± 1.00 , 4.33 ± 0.58 , 3.67 ± 0.58 and 2.67 ± 0.58 larvae/plant/week from 32nd to 50th SW, respectively.

Pod bug, *Clavigralla gibbosa* Spinola, population was start from 36th SW where 0.67 ± 0.58 bugs/plant/week was recorded. The peak population of pod bug 10.67 ± 1.53 bugs/plant/week was noticed from 45th SW. Pod bug population was continuing increased from 36th SW to 45th SW then it was decrease. Kumar and Nath (2005b) reported that the population of *C. gibbosa* started from 23rd November to 7th January (crop maturity) and mean population was 1.67 insect per five plants. Sujithra and Chander (2014) reported the population of tur pod bug between 36th and 44th SMW and with a peak of 3.47 bugs/plant during 38th to 40th SMW. Observation on green bug, *Chinavia hilaris* population range was recorded 0.67 ± 0.58 - 5.00 ± 1.00 bugs/plant/week.

The population was first noticed from 39th SW to continue 50th SW. Two peak populations were recorded from 44th and 45th SW during study period. Spotted pod borer, *Maruca vitrata* was noticed first time from 39th SW with 0.67 ± 0.58 larva/plant/week and 6.67 ± 1.53 larva/plant/week at 50th SW. The peak population (8.67 ± 0.58 larva/plant/week) was recorded from 48th SW. The pest incidence was continuing increased from 39th SW to 48th SW. The population of *M. vitrata* was reported 0.05 to 3.60 larvae per plant in different district of Sri Lanka Bhagwat *et al.*, (1996). Surana (2001) revealed that *M. testulalis* appeared first in the 3rd week of October, which remained active till early January. However, its highest number was recorded in last week of October (0.5 larvae/plant).

Kumar and Nath (2005) found only one generation of the insect that started from 8th November and continued up to 23rd November and mean population was 0.9 larvae per five plants. The blister beetle, *Mylabris phalerata* population was recorded as 0.67 ± 0.58 , 1.00 ± 1.00 , 1.33 ± 0.58 , 1.33 ± 0.58 , 2.00 ± 1.00 , 2.67 ± 1.15 , 1.67 ± 0.58 , 1.67 ± 0.58 , 0.67 ± 0.58 , 0.33 ± 0.58 and 0.33 ± 0.58 beetles/plant/week from respective standard weeks. Pod fly, *Melanagromyza obtuse* (Malloch) infestation was first time noticed from 40th SW where maggots' population was 1.67 ± 0.58 maggots/pod/plant.

The maximum incidence range was 5.00±1.00 maggots/pod/plant and noticed from 45th and 46th SW. Akhauri *et al.*, (2001) reported *M. obtuse* as most serious pest among pod borer-complex of pigeon pea with its peak population (15.60 maggots/plant) in the last week of March (near crop maturity stage). Pandey *et al.*, (2016) noticed the appearance of *M. obtuse* from 42nd SMW with a mean population of 0.10 maggots/plant. Maggot population peaked in 45th SMW with a mean population of 0.30 maggots/ plant during year

2010-11. The peak population of pod borer, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hub.) was recorded as 8.33±0.58 caterpillars/plant/week from 49th SW. First incidence was noticed from 41st SW with 0.33±0.58 caterpillars/plant/week. The pest incidence was approximately similar from 46th SW to 49th SW. Verma (2006) found *H. armigera* continuously attacking the crop from flowering to pod maturation stage *i.e.* from the 3rd week of November to 1st week of February with a range of 0.2 to 5.70 larvae per plant.

Table 1. Population dynamics of insect pest of pegeonpea, *Cajanus cajan* in Bundelkhand during zaid season 2019

Sw	Population (Mean±SD)									
	Jassid	Cowbug	Leaf Webber	Pod Bug	Green Bug	Spotted Pod Borer	Blister Beetle	Pod Fly	Pod Borer	Plume Moth
32	0.33±0.58	0.67±0.19	1.33±0.58	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
34	1.33±1.15	1.33±0.19	1.33±0.58	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
35	0.67±0.58	2.33±0.19	2.33±0.58	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
36	1.67±0.58	2.33±0.51	2.67±0.58	0.67±0.58	-	-	-	-	-	-
37	2.67±1.53	3.00±0.33	3.67±0.58	1.67±0.58	-	-	-	-	-	-
38	2.33±1.53	3.00±0.33	3.67±1.15	2.33±0.58	-	-	-	-	-	-
39	4.00±1.00	2.33±0.19	4.33±0.58	3.33±0.58	0.67±0.58	0.67±0.58	0.67±0.58	-	-	-
40	3.00±2.00	3.00±0.33	5.00±1.00	3.67±0.58	1.33±0.58	1.67±0.58	1.00±1.00	1.67±0.58	-	-
41	5.00±1.00	2.00±0.33	6.67±0.58	4.33±1.53	2.33±0.58	3.00±1.00	1.33±0.58	3.33±0.58	0.33±0.58	-
42	5.00±1.00	1.33±0.19	7.67±0.58	6.00±1.00	3.00±1.00	3.00±1.00	1.33±0.58	3.67±0.58	1.33±0.58	0.33±0.58
43	6.00±1.00	1.67±0.19	8.33±0.58	8.00±1.00	3.33±1.15	4.67±1.15	2.00±1.00	4.67±1.15	3.00±1.00	0.67±0.58
44	6.00±1.73	1.67±0.38	8.33±1.15	9.00±1.00	5.00±1.00	6.00±1.00	2.67±1.15	4.00±1.00	3.67±1.15	1.00±1.00
45	6.00±1.73	2.00±0.33	8.67±0.58	10.67±1.53	5.00±1.00	6.00±1.73	1.67±0.58	5.00±1.00	5.67±1.53	2.67±0.58
46	6.67±2.31	2.33±0.19	9.33±0.58	8.33±2.08	3.67±2.08	6.00±2.00	1.67±0.58	5.00±1.00	7.33±1.53	2.00±1.00
47	4.00±3.46	1.67±0.19	7.00±1.00	2.33±0.58	3.33±2.52	7.33±1.53	0.67±0.58	4.67±0.58	7.67±0.58	3.00±1.00
48	4.67±0.58	1.67±0.19	4.33±0.58	3.33±0.58	3.67±0.58	8.67±0.58	0.33±0.58	4.33±0.58	7.67±1.15	3.33±0.58
49	3.33±0.58	1.33±0.19	3.67±0.58	2.33±0.58	2.67±0.58	7.33±0.58	0.33±0.58	2.67±0.58	8.33±0.58	4.33±0.58
50	2.33±0.58	1.33±0.19	2.67±0.58	2.67±0.58	1.67±0.58	6.67±1.53	-	2.67±0.58	5.67±1.53	3.33±0.58

The peak larval activity of *H. armigera* was observed during the 1st week of December. Bajya and Monga (2009) revealed that the pest *H. armigera* shifted from cotton to pigeon pea from second week of September. The highest population was observed in fourth week of September that reached as high as 5.6 larvae per ten plants. Pest incidence decreased after third week of November (2.2 to 0.3 larvae/10 plants) when pigeon

pea reached maturity and disappeared in the beginning of December. The plume moth, *Exelastis atomosa* (W.) population was 0.33±0.58, 0.67±0.58, 1.00±1.00, 2.67±0.58, 2.00±1.00, 3.00±1.00, 3.33±0.58, 4.33±0.58 and 3.33±0.58 larvae/plant/week. Dwivedi *et al.*, (2013) reported that the pest attained its peak during 44th SW (last week of October to first week of November).

Conclusion

Pigeon pea is important pulse crop in India and this is damaging by various insect by direct or indirect feeding. Insect attacks on crop just after germinate. The maximum damage was recorded at flowering, pod formation and seed formation time. The maximum damage was den by pod borer and pod fly at later stage of the crop during study period.

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